

ENSURING THE RESILIENCE OF ENERGY PUMPS BY INCREASING THEIR VIBRATION RELIABILITY

The rotor sealing system of a high-speed centrifugal pump is one of the most complex and critical units that determine the reliability of the entire unit. This is due to the harsh operating conditions of the seals in combination with high requirements for tightness in all operating modes [1]. In addition to the sealing function, non-contact seals perform an equally important function - they improve the vibration state of the centrifugal machine [2]. Dynamic indicators are especially important for seals of high-speed pumps. When designing sealing systems, it is necessary to coordinate their tightness and reliability, on the one hand, and resource indicators, on the other [3].

The creation of highly loaded pumping equipment with sealing systems for non-standard operating conditions is impossible without taking into account the above factors. Examples of such non-standard products are pumping units for nuclear power plants [4] (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 – Diagram of RCP shaft seal

As indicated in [5], the energy of volumetric losses can be converted into useful energy if, simultaneously, gap seals are used as hydrostatic supports, which are capable of not only having high radial rigidity, but also effectively damping rotor oscillations to acceptable values even in the presence of significant imbalance. This effect is especially significant in the presence of steep velocity and pressure gradients inherent in small gaps of gap seals, on which high pressure drops are throttled, and one of the surfaces belongs to the rotor, which simultaneously rotates and vibrates [6]. In [7], the dynamic characteristics of gap seals as intermediate

supports were investigated. The results of the conducted studies show that when creating sealing systems for modern centrifugal machines, it is necessary to take into account the effect of contactless seals on the dynamic characteristics of the rotor.

Forced joint radial-angular oscillations of the rotor at a constant pressure drop across slotted seals are described by the equations [6]

$$\begin{aligned} & a_1\ddot{u} + a_2\dot{u} + a_3u \mp i(a_4\dot{u} + a_5u)\omega - (\alpha_2\dot{\theta} + \alpha_3\theta)\omega \mp \\ & \mp i(\alpha_4\dot{\theta} + \alpha_5\theta - \alpha_0\theta) = \omega^2 a^* = \omega^2 |a^*| e^{\pm i\omega t}, \\ & b_1\ddot{\theta} + b_2\dot{\theta} + b_3\theta \mp i(b_4\dot{\theta} + b_5\theta)\omega + (\beta_2\dot{u} - \beta_3u)\omega \mp \\ & \mp i(\beta_4\dot{u} + \beta_5u + \beta_0u) = (1 - j_0)\omega^2 \gamma^* = (1 - j_0)\omega^2 |\gamma^*| e^{\pm i\omega t}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Substituting the solution of equations (1) in the form

$$u = u_a e^{i(\omega t + \varphi_u)} = \tilde{u} e^{i\omega t}, \quad \theta = \theta_a e^{i(\omega t + \varphi_\theta)} = \tilde{\theta} e^{i\omega t},$$

we obtain a system of algebraic equations for the complex amplitudes A and Γ

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[-a_1\omega^2 + a_3 + a_4\omega^2 + i(a_2 - a_5)\omega \right] \tilde{u} - \left[(\alpha_3 - \alpha_4)\omega + i(\alpha_2\omega^2 + \alpha_5 - \alpha_0) \right] \tilde{\theta} = A\omega^2 \\ & \left[-(\beta_3 - \beta_4)\omega + i(\beta_2\omega^2 - \beta_5 - \beta_0) \right] \tilde{u} + \left[-b_1\omega^2 + b_3 + b_4\omega^2 + i(b_2 - b_5)\omega \right] \tilde{\theta} = \Gamma\omega^2. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

From the system of inhomogeneous algebraic equations (2), after a series of transformations, we obtain the amplitudes and phases expressed in terms of external perturbations:

$$\begin{aligned} u_a &= \bar{\omega}^2 \sqrt{\frac{(AU_{22} - \Gamma U_{12})^2 + (AV_{22} - \Gamma V_{12})^2}{U_0^2 + V_0^2}}, \\ \theta_a &= \bar{\omega}^2 \sqrt{\frac{(\Gamma U_{11} - AU_{21})^2 + (\Gamma V_{11} - AV_{21})^2}{U_0^2 + V_0^2}}, \\ \varphi_u &= -\arctg \frac{(AU_{22} - \Gamma U_{12})V_0 - (AV_{22} - \Gamma V_{12})U_0}{(AU_{22} - \Gamma U_{12})U_0 + (AV_{22} - \Gamma V_{12})V_0}, \\ \varphi_\theta &= -\arctg \frac{(\Gamma U_{11} - AU_{21})V_0 - (\Gamma V_{11} - AV_{21})U_0}{(\Gamma U_{11} - AU_{21})U_0 + (\Gamma V_{11} - AV_{21})V_0}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Using a similar algorithm, it is possible to obtain expressions for amplitudes and phases for other types of non-contact seals.

For impulse seals [14]:

$$A(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{b_1^2 + \omega^2 b_0^2}{U^2 + \omega^2 V^2}}, \quad \varphi = -\arctg \omega \frac{b_0 U - b_1 V}{b_1 U + \omega^2 b_0 V}. \quad (4)$$

The amplitude and phase frequency characteristics of the auto-balancing system according to the corresponding external influences have the form:

$$A_\tau(\omega) = \sqrt{U_\tau^2 + \omega^2 V_\tau^2} = \sqrt{\frac{U_p^2 + \omega^2 V_p^2}{U^2 + \omega^2 V^2}}, \quad \varphi = \arctg \omega \frac{UV_p - VU_p}{UU_p + \omega^2 VV_p} \quad (5)$$

and for shaftless pump:

$$A(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{U_e^2 + \omega^2 V_e^2}{U_0^2 + \omega^2 V_0^2}}, \quad \varphi(\omega) = \text{arctg} \omega \frac{U_0 V_e - U_e V_0}{U_0 U_e + \omega^2 V_0 V_e}; \quad (6)$$

As can be seen, expressions (3-6) for the amplitudes and phases of various non-contact sealing systems have a similar form.

An analysis of the gap seals' dynamic characteristics showed that the force coefficients of slotted seals are determined by geometric (clearance, radius, length, taper, shape of the leading edges) and operational (pressure drop, operating speed range, physical properties of the pumped medium) parameters. With a purposeful choice of these parameters, it is possible to influence the vibrational state of the rotor and the machine itself.

An important feature of centrifugal machines is that the pressure drops throttled at the gap seals are proportional to the rotor speed. This is due to the self-tightening effect of the rotor, which leads to a positive shift of the critical frequencies.

The operation of non-contact mechanical seals is accompanied by complex non-stationary, high-frequency hydrodynamic processes determined by micron end gaps. For the analytical description of the processes, a model for a sealing in the form of an automatic control system is proposed.

Automatic compensation systems for axial forces acting on the rotor of a multistage centrifugal pump simultaneously perform the functions of a self-adjusting non-contact mechanical seal and a heavily loaded radial-axial hydrostatic bearing. Such systems largely determine the oscillatory state of the rotor.

Axial and radial hydrodynamic forces arising in the throttling gaps of the balancing device are interconnected. As a result, the "rotor-auto-offloading" system, under the influence of the inevitable radial static imbalance, discharge pressure pulsations and harmonic changes in the axial force acting on the rotor perform interconnected forced radial-axial oscillations. At rotational frequencies coinciding with any natural frequency, the resonant amplitudes of these oscillations can exceed the permissible limits, therefore, the determination of resonant rotational frequencies and detuning from them is of great practical importance.

The wheel of a shaftless pump performs independent axial oscillations under the action of kinematic excitation in the form of given radial oscillations due to the static imbalance of the impeller. In this case, the adjustable end throttle creates negative feedback, so the impeller with the support-seal assembly is an automatic control of the end clearance system.

When designing a shaftless pump, it is necessary to compute the axial and angular vibrations of the impeller freely floating in the slotted seals. This will allow to ensure self-tightening of the rotor relative to its oscillations and avoid destabilizing factors by selection of design parameters.

Similar support-balancing devices can also be successfully used in multistage centrifugal pumps.

Using the proposed general approach to the analysis of non-contact seals as automatic control systems, and the algorithm for constructing their dynamic

characteristics at the design stage, it is possible, by changing the geometric parameters of the seals, to ensure their vibration resistance margin.

The studies carried out have shown that all sealing units with throttling gaps or sealing paths filled with a high-pressure medium to be sealed should be considered as dynamic systems. The medium to be sealed, acting on the walls of the sealing paths, affects the dynamic state of the rotor.

It is shown that the purposeful choice of the design parameters of the seals makes it possible to improve the vibrational state of the rotor. In this case, the initially "flexible" dynamically rotor, in combination with properly designed seals, becomes "rigid". The proposed general technique makes it possible to evaluate this effect depending on the design characteristics of the seals and, by changing them at the design stage, to rebuild the "rotor-seals-auto-unloading" system from resonant operating modes.

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ЗАЯВКА НА УЧАСТЬ В КОНФЕРЕНЦІЇ

д.т.н. **Шевченко Сергій Станіславович**, Інститут проблем моделювання в енергетиці ім. Г.Є. Пухова НАН України, старший науковий співробітник, «*Ensuring the resilience of energy pumps by increasing their vibration reliability*».

Е-mail: ShevchenkoSS@nas.gov.ua

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